

Role of Pakistan Navy in Socio-Economic Development of Pakistan's Coastal Belt

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Abstract

Pakistan's coastal belt has its significance because of its geostrategic location. This essay emphasizes Pakistan Navy's critical role in the socio-economic development of the Pakistani coastal belt, along with ensuring security dynamics specifically in the Makran Coast and adjoining areas. A rigorous impact analysis is undertaken to ascertain that how Pakistan Navy's through its public sector development initiatives adds to the national solidarity of the country at large. Following this line of argument an effort is made to assess the efficacy of existing Pakistan Navy's development projects. During the course of study and research, enhanced role of Pakistan Navy is stressed in the overall national security canvas. In crux, likely avenues have been dilated upon to harness Pakistan Navy's maximum potential both in the traditional and non-traditional security domain. The essay also enlists some of the key challenges that factor in realizing a proactive and enlarged role of the Pakistan's Navy.

INTRODUCTION

Maritime nations and the importance of a developed coastline contributing towards socio-economic progress is highly emphasized. It has been noted historically that nations with seafaring population have seen stronger economic growths¹. This fact was also highlighted by Gorshkov, who pointed out that coastlines that have a developed infrastructure have been seen to play an important role in the growth of maritime nations in terms of economy. Some of the biggest cities with infrastructure developments occupy coastal zones². However, the maritime domain of Pakistan has been a victim of oblivion and blindness since the very creation of Pakistan.

The coastal zone of Pakistan lies 1050 km along the Arabian Sea that has been known for its importance in terms of geo- strategic location and also important in terms of geo-politics encompassing it. The trade via sea stands at 95% of the entire international trade and has been contributing about 28% of the GDP³. An unfortunate fact and realization are that despite awareness about the importance of Pakistan's coast and its strategic value, and also the international trade dependency via sea, the coast has suffered neglect owing to non-existent policy focus and the lack of requisite infrastructure. But there has been an increasing demand for the development of infrastructure fuelled by economic growth, a population increase and urbanization. For instance, the contribution of the blue economy in the national economy stands 0.4% of

GDP⁴. This fact and realization make this topic worthy of being highlighted as the development of coastal areas has been known to feed the economic growth of the region.

Few facts about the coastal area under discussion:

-Length of the Coastline: 1050 km⁵

-90% of the households in the coastal communities rely on fishing⁶

-Illiteracy: 90%

-Access to services: Really low

-Sindh Coast- 350 kms-Karachi, Thatta, and Badin districts⁷

-Balochistan Coast-Lasbela near Karachi to Makran coast at the Iranian border.

The article aims to explore the role played by Pakistan Navy in navigating the current coastal situation of Pakistan by initiating or undertaking development projects that have been seen to contribute towards the economic and sociological development of these coastlines, along with identifying the means and methods through which this can be approached to amplify and reap the benefits.

The coastline of Pakistan has been identified as a big contributor towards economy and related activities by providing that crucial land and sea linkage. As identified earlier, the deficit in terms of developed and proper infrastructure has significantly undermined the potential this region holds. Primarily due to continental mind-set of our policy makers in particular, and our nation in general. PN can contribute in terms of policy input and can also provide support to the government

¹ Gorshkov, S. G, *The sea power of the state*, Oxford: Pergamon Press, 1979.

² Ibid

³ Total value of exports and imports for FY 2019-2020 stood at \$31.8 billion. See Economic Survey 2019-2020, Ministry of Finance, Government of Pakistan, http://www.finance.gov.pk/survey/chapter_20/08_Trade_and_Payments.pdf (29 June 2021)

⁴ Press Information Department (PID), Government of Pakistan, "Blue Economy Contribution to GDP" (press release), accessed January 2026

⁵ A Handbook on Pakistan's Coastal Area And Marine Resources, https://www.iucn.org/sites/dev/files/pk_coastal_resources_handbook.pdf (29 June 2021)

⁶ Ibid

⁷ Ibid

efforts with some stand-alone welfare projects or development of these areas for comprehensive national defence; if the country aims to see any hope of a miracle. These regions that have been struck by poverty and lack access to even the most basic services like health and education, depend heavily on such initiatives⁸.

For the socioeconomic conditions of the region to be understood and to understand the problems faced by the locals, it is imperative to develop a picture that can help understand the living conditions and poverty faced by the local populace. For that it is important to look at the indicators that measure these standards and give a statistical picture of the reality on the ground. A better understanding of these facts and figures can help build a stronger argument in favour of how and why these projects are essential and must be undertaken by Pakistan Navy if it aims to help the locals. Two such indicators are Multidimensional Poverty Index and Human Development Index by the United Nations- these two indicators help measure poverty in different regions⁹. The Planning Commission of Pakistan also generates reports for every province that can be used to see the multidimensional poverty index of different regions. The latest survey dates back to 2025, according to which 38.3% of the population is multidimensionality poor, in addition, 12.9% are vulnerable to multidimensional poverty¹⁰.

⁸ According to the Pakistan Bureau of Statistics Labour Force Statistics for 2017-2018, 45% of Baluchistan's population is illiterate (30% males and 63% females).

⁹ United Nations Development Programme, *Human Development Report 2020: The Next Frontier - Human Development and the Anthropocene*, Human Development Report (United Nations, 2020), <https://doi.org/10.18356/9789210055161>.

¹⁰ United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), *Multidimensional Poverty Index 2025 Country Profile: Pakistan* (New York: UNDP, 2025), accessed January 2026, PDF.

In Baluchistan specifically, 70.5% of the populations falls in the multidimensional poverty category¹¹. This is a huge number and this gives the government ample opportunity to utilize resources to alleviate the standard of living and this is also a cry for help if taken seriously.

To that end, a large-scale deep-water port was launched at Gwadar by the Government of Pakistan, with China providing the necessary assistance. In order to provide access to Central Asia, the resource of energy generation while linking it to the world but this initiative is also aimed at elevating poverty and providing an economic boost to the region, hoping to provide the people with a ladder up the social status. The burden falls on Pakistan Navy to take the reins and make efforts towards developing and investing in infrastructure if the coastline of the country aims to see any hope of a miracle.

Pakistan Navy and Coastal Development

Pakistani armed forces have been seen to invest in Baluchistan region from their own budget and resources to help the region economically aiming to uplift the social status of the people residing there. The projects have been dominated mostly by Pakistan Army in terms of initiation in mainland Baluchistan, but Pakistan Navy despite its size and other constraints has still made significant contributions to the developmental projects in the province, especially in Coastal areas and places where PN bases are being located in the mainland.

Although PN has been supporting local communities since it first moved to these areas in early 60s through holding of medical camps and providing basic healthcare, and through provision of food and clean drinking

¹¹ Pakistan Institute of Development Economics (PIDE), *Multidimensional Poverty in Pakistan* (Islamabad: PIDE, 2025), table and analysis of provincial MPI data (2019-20 survey).

water, but a planned move began in 1980s. Since then, Pakistan Navy has initiated many welfare projects in the region, to elevate the living conditions by providing various facilities and services to the local population. The initiation of Coastal Command of Pakistan Navy saw the advent of advancement in welfare projects that have helped heal and advance healthy relationship between the civilians and the military and it has also played an imperative role in building the Civil-Military trust that is elaborated more the later part of this essay.

However, it is a sad reality that majority of the population in Pakistan is blissfully unaware of the dynamics that come into play when it comes to coastal regions, a lack of awareness and knowledge on the subject means that these projects either never come to light, or if they do, they are mostly limited with many hindrances. It is therefore, imperative that Pakistan Navy take up this role of creating awareness of the importance of these regions and their contribution to the overall development of the nation, focusing on welfare projects investment which benefits the local populace immensely. While Pakistan Navy plays this pivotal role of creating awareness by disseminating information about the projects, it must also be noted that it faces certain financial constraints that cannot be unseen or go unnoticed¹². The financial constraint is although a factor that limits much progress and the targets may move forward at a snail's pace, yet it must be acknowledged that this challenge needs to be met head on and Pakistan Navy is required to adopt and adapt and work with the available resources to help bring stability and peace to the coastal region, so that it may be able to seal its interests.

¹² 'Pakistan Naval Expenditure | IPCS', accessed 30 June 2021, http://www.ipcs.org/comm_select.php?articleNo=956

It is not a hidden fact that Pak Navy being the main stake holder in Makran District and for anything happening good or bad on the coast line, will be the most affected or otherwise. Similarly, the share that these welfare projects / avenues will contribute towards the National harmony to 'Win Hearts and Minds' (WHAM) of the people of Baluchistan which is vital to generate good will to counter the threats of growing insurgency in Baluchistan. It is the right time for Pak Navy to devise and adopt a particular strategy for the welfare of Baloch people.

Although, the development of the coast is extremely demanding and challenging due to the very limited budget available with the Pak Navy and similarly, it is not the job of the Navy to develop the Coast.

Defence Budget FY2025-2026 ¹³		
Branch	Percentage of Budget	Total Allocation
Army	45%	1,165 billion
Air force	21%	520 billion
Navy	10%	265 billion
Other Sectors	24%	600 billion
Total		2,550 billion

Yet, when one weighs in the importance of such developmental projects for these regions it is noteworthy how they pave new paths for harmony at a national level, develop cordial

¹³ *The Nation*, "Defence Spending Set to Increase by 20pc," June 10, 2025.

relationships with the people of Baluchistan and ultimately result in progression for the country as a whole. Such gestures of trust and welfare not only help build confidence in the local populace but will also help counter the threat of insurgency in the region, under whose shadow the region has been surviving for quite some time.

With that in mind, Pakistan Navy has initiated various projects including health services, community development, education and unemployment. These projects and initiatives have been met with enthusiasm by the local population who have taken these as a sign of relief in regions that are often neglected. This has also benefited Pakistan Navy in breaking the ice and beginning a journey of developing cordial relationships with the locals and help build trust in the armed forces of Pakistan.

Any delays that might hinder the progress and investment in development projects can affect the nation and Pakistan Navy. Considering the timing and the crucial aspect of these projects, Makran region needs to be the focus of such development undertakings by the Pakistan Navy, who must develop and execute strategies for the welfare of locals, as an established institution operating therein and also in full support of provincial authorities.

Socio-Economic Perspective of Makran Coast

The Makran Region comprises of six towns namely, Ormara, Pasni, Sur Bandar, Gwadar, Pishugan and Jiwani¹⁴. As per latest census data of 2017 the total population of Makran region is 1.48 million¹⁵. Almost 80% of

¹⁴ 'About Balochistan – Government of Balochistan', accessed 30 June 2021, <https://balochistan.gov.pk/explore-balochistan/about-balochistan/>.

¹⁵ See District Wise Census Results 2017, Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, Government of Pakistan, <https://www.pbs.gov.pk/sites/default/files//DIST>

people are dependent on fisheries as a source of their income¹⁶.

The marine resources of Pakistan are also a direct source of livelihood for over a million people and have always contributed towards well-being of fishing communities¹⁷. It is worth mentioning that out of various avenues of economic development, fishing sector has the potential to raise lifestyle of poor people along the coast. In this regard, the Government of Pakistan has given due importance to the fisheries sector within the country's Poverty Reduction Strategy (PRS)¹⁸.

Here it is very essential to identify the impediments that hamper smooth running of fisheries in the Makran region. Some are explained as follows:

Lack of requisite facilities and infrastructure: There are a total of 29 fish processing plants and 36 ice plants along Baluchistan Coast, yet the handling of fish during postharvest process remains unhygienic with no implementation of strict quality control regime. The ice used for fish hold is generally of substandard, thus affecting the overall quality of fish. Lack of requisite machinery and control results in post-harvest losses

[RICT WISE CENSUS RESULTS CENSUS 2017.pdf](#)
(29 June 2021)

¹⁶ A Handbook on Pakistan's Coastal Area And Marine Resources, https://www.iucn.org/sites/dev/files/pk_coastal_resources_handbook.pdf (29 June 2021)

¹⁷ Ibid

¹⁸ 'Accelerating-Economic-Growth-and-Reducing-Poverty-The-Road-Ahead-PRSP-2003.Pdf', accessed 29 June 2021, <http://embassyofpakistanusa.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Accelerating-Economic-Growth-and-Reducing-Poverty-The-Road-Ahead-PRSP-2003.pdf>.

Closure of Pasni Fish Harbour- case in point: Pasni, the fishing town of District Gwadar is significant with regard to its Fish harbour. The employment prospects and business activity in the town is associated with the operationalization of this harbour. However, over past few years same has got non-operational mainly due to silting and dredging issues. The closure of this important economic hub has adverse effects onto the local people living therein. Resultantly the fish catch is reduced because of improper handling of fish at landing sites. During the interview with Fisheries Department Pasni officer, Assistant commissioner, and social worker, it has been revealed that it is the most important point of concern for the local people. The entire business activity is affected very adversely resulting into unemployment and sense of deprivation among the people. Therefore, it's the need of the hour to either fully operationalize the existing harbour or relocate it at a new purpose built state of the art facility on priority, to accrue best out of this natural facility. The government of Baluchistan thus; needs to be pursued at all levels.

Illegal fishing: Considering preservation of fish breeding grounds, fishing through trawlers is not allowed within territorial waters. There are approx. 2600 fishing trawlers registered with Government of Sindh¹⁹. However, a significant number of these trawlers have been observed to be involved in illegal fishing within prohibited limits of Makran coast. It is important to mention that these trawlers use illegal fishing nets to catch commercial fish including small fish near the coastal waters. The catch of small fish affects replenishment stock adversely.

¹⁹ 'Measuring Capacity in Fisheries', accessed 29 June 2021, <http://www.fao.org/3/Y4849E/y4849e0a.htm>.

Nevertheless, there have been several identified underlying causes, reasons why Baluchistan never saw the dawn in terms of development- each diverse with multiple hanging branches. It is a tragedy, however, to realize that the biggest province in the country fell a victim to the largest wave of terrorism, thus crippling whatever chances it had of development. An analysis and evaluation of available content in terms of research, journal articles, newspaper articles, the causes can be narrowed to a few major ones: political instability and the non-serious take of governments towards development in this region, often times reported biased governance, illiteracy in the region, no access to basic facilities like education and healthcare. Other major reasons include insurgency, escalated violence, and the struggle of military to establish cordial relations with the civilians.

**Socio-Economic Projects Initiated by Pakistan Navy:
Pakistan Naval Station Darmaan Jah Hospital Omara:**

Pakistan Navy Built a 100-bed hospital at Darmaan Jah Omara to provide emergency and basic health facilities to local population. This project provides health facilities to the population outside of the major cities. Initially it was inaugurated in 2011, then in 2025 another block was added to expand the facility²⁰.

Bahria School:

Pakistan Navy has played an influential role to provide basic educational facilities to the local population. Pakistan Navy has built Bahria Schools at Gwadar (2010), Jiwani

²⁰ Nuzhat Nazar, "Naval Chief Inaugurates New Block at PNS Darmaan Jah Hospital," *Business Recorder*, April 17, 2025, accessed January 2026, <https://www.brecorder.com/news/40358063/naval-chief-inaugurates-new-block-at-pns-darmaan-jah-hospital>

(2012), and Turbat (2015). These institutions have been providing subsidized education to hundreds of students each year²¹.

Cadet College Omara:

Developed in 2013, Cadet College Omara is a state of art educational facility. This institution offers boarding facilities for the students coming from far off places. The projects aim to improve literary activities for indigenous communities to integrate youth in national socio-economic streams²².

Employment Opportunities:

Presence of the Naval Infrastructural such as Jinnah Naval Base (Omara) has served as a major source of employment for local population. There are reports indicating direct employment of locals from Omara on these facilities. Also, indirect jobs have been created as a result of economic benefits from support services, supply chain, and other such commercial activities²³.

Transforming Civil-Military Relations

The first priority of the Pakistan Navy was evidently to build cordial relations with the locals which has been achieved due to the commitment and investment shown by Pakistan Navy and also because of their non-involvement in military operations in the region. The awareness campaign has also helped manifold in this regard. The Pakistan

Navy has been very vocal about their stance on these projects publicly observing that, the ultimate goal is 'generational improvement' and not just momentary relief²⁴. This means setting out a roadmap for later boots to follow and to help build a better structure that can stand the adversity and break through the glass.

Another thing of importance, that needs to be mentioned here because of the nature of relationship struggles between the military and civil population in the region, is that Pakistan Navy is already getting the stamp of approval for its efforts in the region, and the projects placed forth have helped create an awareness and respect in the local populace. This fact is backed by the argument that out of all the attacks targeted at the armed forces in the region, Pakistan Navy has never been at the receiving end of it. This, if realized, is a great step forward. This shows the civilian population's trust and also sends a message that whatever efforts are being made by Pakistan Navy are not only recognized but are endorsed and respected. A huge achievement in a region that has been under the dark cloud of insurgency and intolerance towards the armed forces.

The small size of Pakistan Navy in comparison with other armed forces has not hindered its commitment towards developmental projects in Makran coast²⁵. Their projects ranging from induction of officers, sailors to create more representation and employment for the locals to establishment of medical facilities and educational institutes to alleviate illiteracy

²¹ Adnan Aamir, "Community-Centric Initiatives of Pakistan Navy in Ormara," *Balochistan Voices*, April 2021, accessed January 2026, <https://www.balochistanvoices.com/2021/04/community-centric-initiatives-of-pakistan-navy-in-ormara/>

²² Usman Ansari, "Pakistan Navy Playing Role in Balochistan's Development," *Business Recorder*, March 23, 2019, accessed January 2026, <https://www.brecorder.com/news/4679895/pakistan-navy-playing-role-in-balochistans-development>

²³ *Pakistan Navy and Blue Economy*, *Daily Times*, September 5, 2025, accessed January 2026, <https://dailytimes.com.pk/1364294/pakistan-navy-and-blue-economy/>

²⁴ Pakistan Institute of Legislative Development and Transparency, "Balochistan: Civil Military Relations," PILDAT Issue Paper: accessed January 8, 2015, www.pildat.org.

²⁵ Pakistan Institute of Legislative Development and Transparency, "Balochistan: Civil Military Relations," PILDAT Issue Paper: (accessed on 20 June 2021, www.pildat.org).

have all been recognized. Although these welfare projects seem like a good start but the size and scale of non-development in the region, it is also imperative to continue efforts towards other welfare projects because as of now they have been deemed insufficient compared to the level of misery faced by the Baloch. Also, most of these facilities are accessible generally to people living in close quarters to the Pakistan Navy establishments, which is a huge limitation in terms of accessibility since welfare projects must aim to be available and accessible to all if it aims to actually be termed a welfare project.

Pakistan Navy, as stated earlier, has more repute with the locals as compared to other armed forces owing to the fact that they do not engage in military operations and have served the locals through various welfare projects including disaster rescue and relief operation during Cyclone PHET in 2010²⁶, that helped save many lost fishermen. This image and repute should be used to the nation's advantage and one crucial effort is to make sufficient funds available to continue investment and development in the coastal region. The importance of such projects, as is visible from this essay, cannot be overstated.

Pakistan Navy has not wavered from its commitment towards social and economic progress in Baluchistan and has proven that by adding various successful welfare projects to the list of already impactful ones. This mission is not only aimed at providing temporary relief, but also has a futuristic vision that can and will provide sustainable growth for the local population.

Pak Navy ongoing projects at Makran Coast

²⁶ 'Pakistani Coastal Areas Brace for Cyclone Phet - CNN.Com', accessed 29 June 2021, <http://www.cnn.com/2010/WORLD/asiapcf/06/03/pakistan.cyclone/index.html>.

Pakistan Coastline

spans over 1050 KM²⁷ along Arabian Sea from Sir Creeks in the East to Dasht River in the West. This area has great geo-political significance and thus, it should come as no surprise that in order to overturn the current situation the stakeholders, especially Pakistan Navy who has a larger stake in coastal areas, need to make serious and committed efforts towards welfare projects. This aims to not only serve Pakistan Navy immensely but would also mean that the locals can have a chance at a better life. To facilitate this FM BAYZAAN was launched to help create awareness about the welfare projects that are being undertaken by the Pakistan Navy.

Pakistan Navy has and is making its presence known in the coastal region. It has the potential, and the capability to undertake projects revolving around humanitarian efforts, disaster relief management along the coasts, and in recent times Pakistan Navy has also been seen to launch various welfare projects to help lift the living standards by providing basic healthcare and educational facilities.

A lack of education and lack of access to it amid restricted financial resources is against the fundamental rights of the people of coastal regions. These areas have been facing decades of neglect, the educational projects initiated by Pakistan Navy aim to rectify this. When financial constraints meet non-accessibility, that is where the governing bodies need to intervene. Without access to education, no one can hope to bring this region out of the poverty-stricken future it is threatened with.

Pakistan Navy being fully aware of these limiting circumstances has established its hold across the entire coastal area of Baluchistan with the hope of bringing relief. Pakistan Navy has made it its utmost priority to

²⁷ 'A Handbook on Pakistan's Coastal Area and Marine Resources', 2016, https://www.iucn.org/sites/dev/files/pk_coastal_resources_handbook.pdf.

establish and improve the facilities linked to educational advancement to provide more opportunities to the people of Baluchistan who rely solely on fishery as their livelihood. This also means improved recruitment opportunities in other sectors and also in recruitment programs initiated by Pakistan Navy including officers, sailors etc.

Pakistan Navy has established institutions that provide free education and has also introduced establishments with reserved seats for the locals to help improve representation chances. What these institutions are doing serves the local populace two ways: first by providing a better chance for recruitment and help them move “up the ladder” that is also both immediate and long term, second, it also makes sure that they finally have a chance to be part of the mainstream society. This also benefits the Pakistan Navy as it increases their pool of talent which can be further exploited for more recruitments.

The highlight of these educational projects is Cadet College Ormara. It is a large-scale institute in Baluchistan that also supports the initiatives of the federal government to help improve literacy in the region. The institute provides education from class 8th to the Higher Secondary School Certificate (HSSC). This facility has been equipped with the require academic support, accommodation, recreational facilities, designated prayer area and administrative support, in addition to other miscellaneous support. Perhaps the most noticeable feature among all is the fact that this facility has been made accessible to the Baloch population by keeping a significant number of seats reserved.

The scheme is generous and works perfectly in accordance with inclusion principle by making sure that the Baloch students have their expenditures covered fully by the government of Pakistan. This scheme also allows the Baloch cadets to be selected and recommended for Inter-Services Selection Board (ISSB) through which they can

ultimately land a job in Pakistan Navy. It is also ensured that this scheme is available to candidates from humble backgrounds.

A good secondary education needs to be backed up by a good primary education as well, for this purpose Bahria Foundation introduced facilities for primary level education to help strengthen the educational foundation²⁸. The facilities include Bahria Model College Ormara, Bahria Model School Jiwani, Bahria Model School Gwadar and Bahria Model School Turbat.

The details of some of the ongoing projects are as under:

Pak Navy Recruitment & Selection Centre Gwadar:

In order to enhance representation of Baloch in armed forces PN Recruitment & Selection Centre (PNR&SC) at Gwadar has been established, (in addition to PNR & SC Quetta). The recruitment of candidates from coastal and adjoining areas i.e., Ormara, Pasni, Gwadar, Turbat and Jiwani is aimed to increase induction of officers, sailors, and civilians in Pakistan Navy substantially from Baluchistan and in particular from Makran Coast.

Recruitment Campaigns for Baloch:

Since 2007, Pakistan Navy undertook vigorous recruitment campaign in Baluchistan to create awareness amongst the people. As a result, large number of candidates have joined Pakistan Navy in officer, sailor, and civilian category.

Naval Cadet Scheme for Bloch:

For the welfare of Baloch, Naval Cadet scheme has been reintroduced exclusively for candidates hailing from Baluchistan. Each year 25 candidates are given admission in

²⁸ ‘Bahria Foundation | A Trusted Partner’, accessed 29 June 2021, <https://bahriafoundation.com/>.

Cadet College Ormara. Subsequently, these candidates after qualifying ISSB will join Pakistan Naval Academy as Pak Navy cadets. These cadets are studying 100% free including monthly stipend amount.

Short Service Commission (SSC) for Baloch:

Induction of talented and bright Bloch youth (graduates) in Pak Navy through Short Service Commission has also been started and few officers have already joined PN as commissioned officer.

Establishment of PNS DARMAN JAH

Pak Navy has recently established a 100-bed hospital "PNS DARMAN JAH" at Ormara with all latest facilities to provide medical facilities to locals of Coastal Belts. The hospital is the first ever modern medical facility in the area and has brought great relief to locals as previously patents were being sent to Karachi or Quetta for basic health facilities. The Federal Government of Pakistan has appreciated the role played by Pakistan Navy in development of coastal areas, particularly the Makran Coast, through various projects and initiatives. Baluchistan's Chief Minister is also among the prominent figures who have lauded Pakistan Navy's efforts in uplifting the region²⁹. He also made a commitment to provide funding to help the generous cases during his inaugural speech of Cadet College Ormara; Hostel and Academic Wing.

Conclusion

One of the key observation of this study is lack of documented material focused on the Pakistan Navy's role in the growth and development of the coastal regions. The subject remains untapped either by design or default underrating the criticality of the

Pakistan's Navy diversified potential. Thus, most of the local literature is extracted from official and semi-official reports and seminar proceeding conducted at National Institute of Oceanography (NIO), National Centre for Maritime Policy Research (NCMPR) and Pakistan Institute of Maritime Affair (PIMA), feasibility studies prepared by Sindh and Baluchistan Coastal Development Authority (BCDA/SCDA). Newspapers articles have also contributed towards the limited study focusing on the developmental projects and the impact of these projects on the growth of the region. The data overall is quite limited specifically in the context of this study.

Militaries around the world are employed in the aid to civil power, humanitarian assistance, development, and other welfare projects. Pakistan Armed forces are also contributing towards welfare projects for nation building. Lessons from the past clearly defined that military is not the only solution to a political problem. Baluchistan coast non - developmental issue is an issue of mistrust and Balochi people's trust has to be re-earned now by whatever it takes. PN has already initiated measures in this regard. Now, it is the right time to further enhance its scope from a limited policy to a national strategy. The same is only possible if right steps are initiated with true spirit and full conviction. Majority of Baloch people do not want independence they just want to be heard. Pakistan Navy in its limited domain can set example for others to follow.

Recommendations

After analyzing the potential of Pakistan Navy to further enhance its welfare strategy based on the finding of its existing projects during research, following recommendations are made for more effective and efficient contribution of Pakistan Navy to contribute to maintaining peace and stability in and around

²⁹ Saleem Shahid, 'Balochistan CM Lauds Navy's Role in Education, Health', DAWN.COM, 4 September 2014, <http://www.dawn.com/news/1129777>.

Makran coast region and to remove resentment of angry Baloch locals:

- a. National Conference on “Baluchistan coastal areas for enhancing the pace of development and prosperity” to be organized by PN for awareness of masses.
- b. PN should bring members of civil society, media, policy makers, thinkers, and politicians on one page for enhancing the pace of development of coastal areas and prosperity for the sake of stronger Pakistan.
- c. To provide better education, all teachers in government schools in Baluchistan must be familiarized with best teaching techniques through short courses at Bahria colleges/PNS RAHNUMA and all teachers in Bahria model schools and colleges in coastal areas must be inducted from Karachi or other part of Pakistan to improve education standard of Baluch students.
- d. Federal Government and Ministry of Defense may be approached by PN for provision of extra funds for execution and completion of welfare projects at Makran coast region.
- e. PN should enforce fishery laws through MSA to save depleting fish resources in coastal areas. Use of small size nets is to be strictly prohibited.
- f. Installation of tracking system on all trawlers to keep an eye on illegal fishing in prohibited areas (inside 35NM of EEZ).
- g. PN should arrange frequent media campaign to highlight beautiful locations of Baluchistan coastal areas.
- h. Public-private partnership needs to be started for development of Baluchistan coast. Where government capacity is limited, private sector with its dynamic character can make up for the shortfall. Therefore, PN should pursue private sector through vast publicity of Sahil welfare association (SWA) in print media.
- j. Establishment of Baluchistan Welfare projects Dte at NHQ to look after PN welfare projects being undertaken at Makran Coast. The directorate will also monitor the

effectiveness of

these operations to maintain peace, security in the region.

- k. Seek options for provision of more jobs to Balochi people in Pakistan Navy, Gwadar Port Authority, and local administration etc.
- l. Earliest completion of Cadet College Ormara purpose-built building so as to raise number of N cadets from 25 N-cadets to 100 N- cadets per year.
- m. Pursue Govt for provision of fund for Construction of 100 bedded hospital at Gwadar and conversion of PNS Darman Jah Hospital from C to A class hospital to afford better health facilities to Balochi people.
- n. Provision of fresh water to the general masses of Ormara, Pasni and Gwadar. In this regard Federal Government may be pursued for construction of Basol dam, Reverse Osmosis plants and water stowage facilities.
- p. Extension of FM BAYZAAN telecast to other distant location of the Makran Coast. Presently, the same is limited to 60 km of radios from Gwadar. Issuance of weather warning to fishermen through FM BAYZAAN and awareness of general masses may be undertaken through this project by telecasting valuable programmers.
- q. Institutionalization of technical schools at Gwadar for provision of electrical and mechanical training and diploma certification to locals.
- r. Establishment of cold STORAGE facility at Gwadar, Pasni, Jiwani and Ormara through continues pursuance with Federal government for the welfare of local fishermen.
- s. Pursue Federal Government for the establishment of ship maintenance facility at Gwadar bay due to better business opportunity being in close proximity of world important traffic lane of Gulf of Oman.
- t. Pursue government of Baluchistan for early completion of jetties at Jiwani, Peshukan, Surbandar and Pasni. Such

activities have gravely perturbed the local populace and have developed THEIR mistrust IN government institutions and PN also.

u. PN may start Coastal safari to attract tourists and create Maritime domain awareness among PEOPLE.

v. Provision of assistance for dredging of Pasni fish Harbor Channel to make it operational.

w. Adoption of government schools in vicinity of all PN units in coastal areas and early construction of purpose-built building of PN Model Schools at Jiwani, Pasni and Turbat.

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